

A Metaethical Review In Defense of the Divine Command Theory

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Abstract

The metaethical review presented in this essay provides a deductive defense of the Divine Command Theory through the examination of ontological requirements for moral realism. Utilising Hume's Law, it is argued that descriptive "is" statements which imply facts, cannot yield prescriptive "ought" statements of which the content is value-based. The text also contends that naturalist metaethical theories, which are predominant in atheistic frameworks, necessarily entail moral relativism because they lack a transcendent grounding for binding moral duties. At the core of the proposed argument lies the idea that if God does not exist, objective moral values do not exist and therefore atheistic moral frameworks are incompatible with morally realist perceptions. Through one additional claim, the argument also becomes a theistic argument: Since the existence of objective moral values are more evident than the argumentative methods that are utilised to object to

them, a divine source as a prescriber must exist. A non-naturalist atheistic moral framework named Platonic atheism has also been criticized via various arguments. In addition to the defenses for the premises of the argument, a critical analysis on scientific approaches is also put forward. The review concludes that only a framework involving an ontologically superior being can resolve the "is-ought" gap and rationalize moral behavior at the individual level to eliminate the bindingness problem in all scenarios.

Keywords: Hume's law, command theory, metaethics, divine, moral realism, platonic atheism

Introduction

The discussions on moral philosophy, particularly when addressed to a broader audience, require several conceptual and intentional clarifications due to their highly delicate nature. Indeed, even those who have spent a significant amount of their time reading on this very subject may not be able to avoid the most obvious errors of thought due to the lack of conceptual clarity. Thus, I have decided to begin with brief but vitally significant explanations about the sub-branches of moral philosophy. Then, in order not to be misunderstood, the implication of the argument to be formulated in the following pages will be elaborated upon.

In the analytic tradition, ethics is divided into three main branches. Namely, these are metaethics, normative ethics, and applied ethics. Metaethics is a

field of study that focuses on the theories that aim to provide plausible explanations for the origins of morality. Questions such as "Is morality objective?" or "On what basis do we ground our understanding of morality?" are examined under metaethics. Therefore, the realism and anti-realism discussion, which we will discuss later, as well as the epistemic validity and valuation of moral propositions, are also metaethics-related issues.

For the sake of our purpose here, we can reduce the metaethical positions to two:

1. Naturalist Theories
2. Divine Command Theories

Normative ethics, on the other hand, is a field that aims at exploring the constituents of moral actions. Fundamentally, it is about how we distinguish between right and wrong (it might be based on rationality or the combined utilities of the society). As its name indicates, normative ethics examines the general principles of how one *ought to act* to be a morally good agent. To prevent any misconception, normative ethics has nothing to say on the source(s) of the aforementioned moral principles and focuses on what makes an action right or wrong from an ethical perspective. In order to better understand, we have to take a look at the normative ethical positions and their compatibility with contradicting metaethical positions so that the two branches are distinguished from one another with due clarity. Here are the three positions of normative ethics:

1. Deontological (Kantian) Ethics
2. Consequentialist Ethics
3. Virtue Ethics

My claim is that there can be two individuals who are both in support of consequentialism, where one of them is an atheist who believes in a naturalist metaethical theory, and the other is a faithful classical theist who grounds his ethical position on a God-sent revelation. In this regard, this study will be, mostly if not wholly, about metaethics. That is to say, other irrelevant discussions will be disregarded.

Before the formulation of our argument, it is necessary to state what we are *not* going to advocate for in this study. An analogy might help us at this point: Some theists claim that God designed our eyes, either directly or through the evolutionary process. Obviously, this claim does not make such an implication that theists see better than atheists or that atheists are blind. Similarly, the claim that our moral perceptions are given by God and that the origin of morality lies in God's character and nature does not imply that atheists are less moral agents (Doko, 2020). Clearly, there are basic moral intuitions that enable us all to act morally. What is going to be claimed in this argument is that if God with certain attributes does not exist, those intuitions are doomed to be subjective. In other words, an atheistic metaethical position entails the rejection of moral realism.

To be a morally acting agent is notably different from providing an ontological basis for moral propositions. For instance, assume that there is an absolutely talented basketball player who knows about and abides by the rules of this sport. In this context, the said player can be regarded as a good player. However, this player most certainly would know and, without any hesitation, admit that these rules are determined by the human mind. Thus, to be a good basketball player does not necessitate the belief that those rules possess objective value. Similarly, there is no such prerequisite of approving the objectivity of morality to be a moral agent. Therefore, when we argue that if atheism is true, then there are no objectively valid moral propositions, we obviously do not claim that atheists are immoral witches.

Hume's Law: Deriving an *ought* from an *is*

It is necessary to provide explanatory and defensive analysis about the content of the premises before putting our argument into a logical form. Since Hume's law is at the core of the whole argument, we shall begin by analyzing it.

The underlying distinction of Hume's Law is the distinction between factual propositions and axiological propositions. Factual propositions correspond to the "is" part of the title above, whereas axiological ones correspond to the "ought" part. Factual propositions, as it might be inferred from the naming, simply describe the

facts out there in the universe. Thus, they possess a pretty descriptive nature, whereas any statement about morality is inherently prescriptive. The best examples of factual propositions are scientific propositions. Generally speaking, the content of factual propositions is empirically observable. Surely observation is not necessarily the only way to test the accuracy of factual propositions. If there are entities such as abstract concepts of numbers or supernatural beings, they are not observable; however, propositions that describe them are also factual.

Hume's law indicates that one "can not derive an ought from an is" or, more decently, that purely descriptive premises never entail normative conclusions (Russell, 2010). Accordingly, if your argument consists of only factual premises, then the concluding premise will necessarily have to be factual.

Since we have used both the term "premise" and the term "proposition", some might get confused. Although there is not a huge difference between them, premise is technically utilized for steps that are put forward in logical argumentations, whereas proposition is a declarative sentence which is evaluated in terms of truthfulness. With that being stated, let us go back to our argument.

Another significant distinction is between moral realism and moral anti-realism. Moral realism is a philosophical view that claims that at least one moral proposition, as a subcategory of axiological

propositions, is true or false. It is important to remember that in this context, truth implies objective validity. Therefore, these moral propositions must be true or false regardless of the time, place, or society in which we live. Social and cultural norms are of no significance. For instance, even if all human beings agree upon the idea that the act of rape is morally acceptable, rape will remain evil. And indeed, there are societies, either actively living or lived in the past, where we observe such instances that are "indisputably" immoral, yet practiced by the consensus of that particular society.

It is no secret that the crimes perpetrated against humanity in the past (the Nazi Holocaust, for instance) were largely adhered to by large masses. In addition to that, in some ancient societies, when the ruler died, his wives/servants, etc., would be killed because of the distorted belief in the afterlife. We can increase the number of samples by mentioning societies where human sacrifice is observed as a commonly practiced custom. Moral anti-realism, on the other hand, refuses to attribute any intrinsic value to morality. Moral rules are nothing more than the sum of particular value judgements and do not imply any objectively valid truth.

Formation of the Argument

First and foremost, we will claim that if an ontologically superior entity in the role of a God by whom at least one moral rule is prescribed does not exist, then all meaningful propositions are confined

to being factual and thus can not constitute a normative and prescriptive nature. Besides, considering Hume's law as a logical necessity, we will aim to demonstrate that in a Godless world, one can not infer objectively valid axiological propositions since we can not derive an axiological proposition if all fundamental propositions are factual.

P1. If there are objectively valid axiological propositions, then they must be either deduced from fundamental laws (which makes them derived laws) or taken as fundamental laws from which all sorts of propositions are deduced.

P2. If God does not exist, all fundamental laws are necessarily natural laws.

P3. All natural laws are factual (descriptive).

P4. One cannot derive an axiological proposition from factual propositions.

P5. At least one axiological proposition is either true or false.

Conclusion: Therefore, God exists.

If all of the premises above are true, then the conclusion is inevitably going to be true. Surely, I presume the laws of logic as the starting point in producing knowledge. Without them, we can not even talk about an argument in the very beginning. It is also important to note that this moral argument is at the intersection of both moral philosophy and philosophy of religion. We just make one addition to the claim in favor of divine command theory and

provide defenses against morally nihilistic perceptions. Through this addition, the argument also becomes a theistic argument for the existence of God. Now, we will try to give defenses for each of the five premises and respond to potential objections that might be raised against them.

The first premise is true by logical necessity. Once a person affirms the basic principles of logic, this premise can not be objected to. The Aristotelian law of excluded middle must be refuted for it to be regarded as inaccurate. Since we already presumed the principles of logic to be accurate as a starting point, no further defense is needed for the first premise.

The second premise refers to the most popular view among atheists. It is the naturalist thesis that rejects the existence of any supernatural entity. Accordingly, the strongest explanatory power for the existence of the universe in which we live (or some other potential universes) is embedded in a naturalist interpretation of it. In this naturalist framework, one can not talk about ontological beings other than the laws of nature and material existents, which are transformed, subjected to change, generated, or dissolved by those laws. The wording “by the laws of nature” does not imply any attribution of willpower to those laws. They are simply described as the generalized statements of the regularities in the natural world.

According to the naturalist view, one can not talk about a God, at least in the classical sense of the term. By the classical sense of the term, obviously,

we imply a transcendent God who is not bounded by time and space. My claim is that if naturalism is true and thus such a God does not exist, all fundamental laws are natural laws which constitute factuality. Thus, the second premise is true. However, some might object to the naturalist thesis and still internalise an atheistic philosophical position. There is no logical contradiction, for instance, between a belief in the existence of supernatural beings such as Jinn or demons and the disbelief in the existence of a Creator. However, one might also believe in a God who is a physical being bound by the Natural World as well. Although there is no problem in following such views in terms of logic, it is demonstrable that internalising such views is simply unreasonable. That is, for a view to be depicted as inaccurate, it does not have to be illogical necessarily.

Yet, some can criticize our defense above by arguing that it is actually fighting the ghost and that there are alternative forms of atheism which are not as radical and unreasonable as the stated examples. At this point, Platonic atheism is worthy of examination.

Critique of Platonic Atheism

The only serious attempt for a non-physicalist form of atheism in the literature is Platonic atheism. This position is an objection to our second premise, and it seems to be the only form of atheism that meets the necessities for compatibility with moral realism. It is an

alternative to both theism and morally nihilistic forms of atheism (Steinhart, 2023). The reason why it is called "platonic" is its evocative nature to the Platonist theory of ideas. Accordingly, moral concepts such as justice and mercy do exist as beings transcendent of time and space. To better understand this view, it might be helpful to take a look at the ontological perceptions of mathematical objects. One of the most popular views about the ontology of mathematics among mathematicians is Platonism. For instance, if we think of geometric objects, there is no such thing as a perfect triangle or a circle in the natural world. The question is, should we consider them as fabricated products of our minds, or are they entities existing in some other realm? The application of the same question to moral concepts instead of the mathematical ones, and a response in favor of the latter view, is where the Platonic perception of morality comes from.

This view can be criticized in terms of several aspects. If Platonic atheism is true, then morality would exist even if there were no morally active agents like humans. To clarify, non-human natural beings with no willpower to comprehend moral concepts are regarded as morally passive agents. On reasonable ground, nobody can accuse a mother cat of killing its own babies. Morally passive agents are included in moral discussions only in the case of a potential interaction with morally active agents. Thus, morality seems to be meaningful as long as there are conscious human beings around. Then,

how could it be the case that moral concepts exist in a realm where there is no morally active agent?

Another problem with this view is about the bindingness of morality. No natural being, as far as ordinary humans experience and make sense of the world, can act in contradiction with mathematical facts. Some might deny the existence of mathematical objects, but their application in engineering or other natural science-related fields is objectively validated. To put it more simply, a person who denies the existence of numbers can not escape from them while shopping in a marketplace. However, this situation does not apply to moral objects. Our actions can be contradictory to what might be called "moral rules" since moral propositions and conceptions are prescriptive. A human being possesses the capability to act against the prescribed rules of morality even if he or she approves the objective validity of those rules. For example, let us assume that the following propositions correspond to a truth:

P1. To be merciful is good

P2. To be selfish is evil

The fact that these propositions are true does not imply any prescription for humans to act in accordance with their contents, nor does it rationalise such actions. Therefore, Platonic atheism is incapable of providing objective responses to the question of "why ought I to act morally?"

In addition to these problems, one more epistemological critique can be cited. This critique is also applicable in the context of the Platonist view on mathematics. At the center of this critique lies the idea that to know something (whatever it is), one must go through a causal interaction with the object of this process. Since moral objects are transcendent of time and space, which implies that they do not engage in causal relations, there is no possibility for humans to be able to acquire knowledge about them. This counter-argument is very hard to defend coherently from a theistic perspective. Indeed, the means by which humans acquire knowledge about God also becomes questionable since God himself is characterised as transcendent of time and space in classical theism.

The third premise is based on the fact-value distinction. Even though there are some philosophers, such as Hilary Putnam who reject the distinction between fact and value, the predominant opinion among naturalist philosophers is that natural laws are factual. And in fact, the rejection of this distinction still does not imply the rejection of the fact that natural

laws are factual. What is denied is rather the exclusiveness of facts and values, not the existence of facts and values.

The fourth premise has already been clarified, and an explanation in defense of it is provided above, where we presented Hume's Law. And indeed, there are no philosophers, at least to our knowledge, who reject the factuality of natural

laws. However, metaphysical or, as some call it, 'ontological' naturalists usually tend to reject the fact-value distinction. Therefore, an elaboration upon Hume's law is needed since one might aim to challenge it by arguing for the possibility of such a logical derivation. In this regard, we will now defend the fourth premise and try to suggest responses to hypothetical objections.

Hume's law is one of the basic laws of deductive reasoning. Accordingly, it is not contingent to derive an axiological proposition from factual propositions. In order to better understand this, we have to take a look at the fundamental features of deductive reasoning and its implications. The semantic approach, which the analytic tradition internalises, argues that an argument is valid if there is no alternative interpretation of the argument left, whereas its premises are all true, yet the conclusion is false. The famous example of it is the following;

P1. All humans are mortal

P2. Socrates is a human

Conclusion: Socrates is mortal

This is an example of valid deductive reasoning. At the core of this type of reasoning, there lies the idea that the conclusion is embedded in the premises. If the premises are true, the conclusion is true by logical necessity. One of the most significant differences of the analytic tradition is the utilisation of such reasoning by philosophers in their argumentations. Their purpose is to provide

coherent premises and a conclusion that is based on them. If one wants to object to the conclusion, they are obliged to demonstrate the inaccuracy of at least one premise or object to the deductiveness of the reasoning itself. This method enables the philosophers to discuss philosophical problems in a more coherent manner. And indeed, our argument as a whole is based on such deductive reasoning, and the defense which we will provide in favor of our fourth premise is going to be based on such argumentation. Let us begin and try to put forward an argument in which we derive an ‘ought’ from an ‘is’ and examine its possibility from a logical perspective.

P1. Yusuf killed Ali

P2. Killing Ali makes Ali suffer

P3. Ahmet did not make anybody suffer

Conclusion: Yusuf ought not to have killed Ahmet

All of the premises above are factual premises. Yet, the conclusion is axiological. Even if the conclusion is true -it might not be- this type of argument is invalid in the sense that it is incapable of meeting the requisites of what is described above as deductive reasoning. In fact, one can accept the three premises above and still be in denial of the conclusion. There is no logical obstacle for someone to deny the conclusion without the rejection of at least one premise. The person who objects to the conclusion can be

accused of unscrupulousness, but not of being ignorant about logic.

In order to derive a logically valid conclusion, one must add an axiological proposition to the premises.

P1. We ought not to kill innocent human beings

P2. Ali was an innocent human being

Conclusion: Ali ought not to have been killed

Given this set of premises, the conclusion derived from them is undeniably accurate since the acceptance of two premises logically necessitates the conclusion. This is a valid example of deductive reasoning, and as it is obvious, the first premise is axiological just like the conclusion. To conclude our defense in favor of the fourth premise, it is impossible to logically demonstrate the necessity of an axiological conclusion by means of utilising only factual premises. Therefore, Hume’s law seems to be accurate.

So far, we have demonstrated the incompatibility of atheism with a morally realistic framework. However, an atheist can consistently internalise a morally anti-realistic framework without objecting to the four premises for which we have provided defenses.

Therefore, one more defense against moral anti-realism is needed to complete our argument. Yet, we see the benefit in evaluating the evolutionary views as potential “scientific”

objections to our argument. Especially those who regard themselves as the advocates of science may argue for a scientific explanation to ground objective morality. In fact, with the rise of scientism, plenty of neo-atheist scientists became popular among the public. One of those popular names is the famous neuroscientist Sam Harris, who claims in his book “The Moral Landscape” to explain and ground morality by purely scientific means (Harris, 2010). He argues against moral relativism and challenges the distinction between facts and values, stating that the values are a specific type of facts about the well-being of conscious creatures. His opinions are not seen as eligible by most naturalist philosophers; nonetheless, he was exceedingly popular, especially throughout the 2010s. To argue against Harris, we are going to develop a scientific approach by making use of the Neo-Darwinian theory of evolution.

Evolutionary Argument Against Scientism

In our case, only two major principles of the theory of evolution are of significance. Our argument is based on the principle of natural selection and Neo-Darwinism. Natural selection is the main mechanism through which species adapt to their environment and change (Futuyma and Kirkpatrick). Accordingly, organisms with advantageous heritable traits have more chances to reproduce and pass on the beneficial traits to their offspring. Over time, these more advantageous

traits become more commonly observed within the population. This is the process of natural selection.

Neo-Darwinism is the integration of Darwin's theory of evolution by natural selection with genetics (Futuyma and Kirkpatrick). Accordingly, the source of the genetic variation is the mutations in the DNA of an organism. Mutations happen randomly and are independent of the needs of the species. In this regard, mutations can be beneficial, harmful, or neutral.

Taking these two components of the theory of evolution as accurate, which Sam Harris and other adherents of scientism are not expected to dispute, it is at least not rational to accept Harris's view on morality. It is noteworthy that, unlike the previous evaluations, our claim here is not logical but rather probabilistic. If Neo-Darwinian evolution is true, a scientific endeavor to ground moral realism is very likely to fail. We are going to cite two main reasons for this improbability.

First and foremost, we have to take a look at the behaviors of unconscious animals and their evolutionary explanations to understand one of our reasons. Consider bees, for instance. Darwin (1871) himself also thought the same example in his book “Descent of Man”, and he concluded that it is highly probable that morality is largely shaped by the evolutionary process and thus has no intrinsic value. If we evolved differently, our conception of morality would also differ accordingly.

Bees live in what might be depicted as a strict communal life, within which a member of the

commune can be self-sacrificed for altruistic excuses. In fact, self-sacrifice for reproductive altruism is a cornerstone of their eusocial structure. Moreover, in many cases, this altruism is not voluntary but rather enforced. Now, assume that bees have evolved by means of the same

evolutionary process thanks to which they got this altruistic set of behaviours, but also became conscious to the extent that humans are. Would the same altruistic behaviours occur under such conditions? It appears that there is no empirical ground to think otherwise. Since those enforced altruistic behaviours are in contradiction with the general conceptions of morality in the human mind, a purely scientific explanation of morality must be anti-realistic. Furthermore, certain types of actions that are considered immoral can be explained through the structural features of the process of evolution. To give you an idea, theft is regarded as immoral and unlawful in all societies, from the most primitive ones to the contemporary ones, without exception. Given this fact, let us go through a thought experiment. Imagine two separate tribes, in one of which theft is commonly practiced, whereas the other strictly forbids and ruthlessly punishes theft. In case of a potential clash between the two tribes, the possibility that the latter wins the battle would be pretty high. In this context, the immorality of the act of theft is not discovered in some ideal world by the human mind but rather made up for survival reasons.

The second reason we will introduce is based on the teleology of evolution. Evolutionary principles

that we cited above depict a world where species aim at two things: Survival and reproduction. If we leave the million-year-old history of evolution behind and focus on the question of “How ought I to act”, it becomes clear that a fairly subjectivist perception of morality is faced with. In fact, individuals can justify all acts that contribute to the possibility of the transfer of their genes to future generations. As long as there is not a surveillance watching every single individual and as long as there is not a higher authority to punish certain types of acts, such as homicide, (an ugly man can rationally commit homicide a handsome guy because the handsome guy decreases the possibility of him finding a partner for reproduction), many immoral acts would be justified from individualistic perspectives.

Due to the reasons we have mentioned above, a scientific trial to ground objective morality is not possible. In fact, it is not in the purview of science to say anything about fields such as morality. Science only describes things as they are in the outer world. Nevertheless, we need more than a description to explain morality.

The final premise of our argument was about moral realism. It would not be absurd to claim that we can presume a morally realistic framework as long as the contrary is not proven. We can rationally take it as granted because, as humanity, we have several fundamental and indispensable axiological beliefs thanks to our intuitions. However, we will cite an epistemological argument to ground our rational

take in favor of moral realism. The argument is as follows:

P1. To rationally reject moral realism, one needs to give rational arguments

P2. The truthfulness of the premises of rational arguments is not as evident as some of the moral principles

Conclusion: It is not possible to rationally reject moral realism

Many philosophical arguments against moral realism can be developed. However, the evidence of those philosophical suppositions is much less than the evidence of some moral propositions. And indeed, they appear to be more speculative and disputable. For example, the evilness of acts such as infanticide, incestuous relations, or the act of rape seems to be less disputable than the premises of arguments against moral realism.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has established a deductive argument to assert that a moral framework exists in which an ontologically superior being who prescribes moral rules promises absolute justice, intending to rationalise moral acts in all scenarios and ensure the bindingness of the prescribed rules. We have also presented defenses for each premise of the argument and responded to potential objections. One more analysis of the scientific attempts to ground the existence of objective moral rules has been made. Hence, it has

been demonstrated that an atheistic perception of the world entails a morally relativistic position which is unlikely to be true. For the final remark, to object to this theistic defense of moral realism, at least one of its premises presented herein must be refuted.

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